

Perceived and Structural Barriers to Maternal Health Care in Urban Slums of Kathmandu Valley, Nepal: A Qualitative Inquiry

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ABSTRACT

Background: Despite the physical accessibility of health facilities, maternal health care access is still a major problem in urban slum areas where socio-economic and structural inequalities are still present. Women in informal settlements may experience unrecognized obstacles to accessing antenatal, delivery, and postnatal services. The availability is not sufficient to guarantee continuity of care, especially for marginalized groups. But, there is little qualitative study that has examined the interaction between perceived and structural barriers to access of maternal health care in Nepal. The purpose of this study was to understand the perceived and structural barriers to maternal health care access for women.

Methods: The study design involved in-depth interviews (IDIs) and focus group discussions (FGDs) in selected urban slum settlements of Kathmandu Valley in 2024. Purposive and snowball sampling were used to select women of reproductive age who had recent maternal health care experiences. The semi-structured interview guides were used to gather data and audio-recorded with consent. Thematic analysis was conducted on transcripts using NVivo software and matrix coding with ordinal scaling was used to examine relationships between themes.

Results: Four main themes were identified: perceived absence of barriers, financial barriers, structural barriers, and discontinuity of care. Participants reported no significant problems with proximity of facilities, but there was an “illusion of access.” The most important barrier to continued utilization was financial constraints, especially the cost of diagnostics and follow-up visits. Indirect costs were further elevated by structural barriers as referral dependency and transportation issues. Financial barriers had a strong association with discontinuity of care, and perceived access had weak relationships with actual utilization, suggesting a perception reality gap.

Conclusion: Financial and structural barriers are interrelated and create a disconnection in maternal health care access in urban slums, despite the perceived availability. Policies should lower out-of-pocket expenses, enhance primary care, and enhance transport and referral systems to promote equitable maternal health service utilization.

KEYWORDS: Maternal health, urban slums, access barriers, continuity of care, Nepal.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Despite significant progress under global development frameworks, maternal morbidity and mortality remain disproportionately high, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) (WHO, 2019; United Nations, 2015). Access to essential maternal health services as antenatal care (ANC), skilled birth attendance (SBA), and postnatal care (PNC) is at the heart of improving maternal and neonatal results. Access is not just about services, however, and is influenced by a complex mix of socio-economic, cultural and health system factors (Campbell & Graham, 2006; Graham et al., 2016). This complexity is heightened in fast-growing urban settings, where inequalities within cities can be masked by overall measures of progress.

The world has undergone a population shift, with more and more people living in urban areas. Although it is generally believed that urban areas offer better access to health services, this is not true for all urban areas, especially informal settlements or slums (Montgomery, 2009; Satterthwaite, 2016). The main features of urban slums are excess, insecure tenure, inadequate infrastructure, and restricted access to basic services, health care (UN-Habitat, 2020). Women in these settings are exposed to a number of and multiple and intersecting challenges that limit their access to maternal health services effectively, despite their proximity to the

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services (Fotso et al., 2009). These conditions highlight the importance of examining not just physical access but also the broader determinants of service utilization.

The government has taken several steps to improve maternal health results in Nepal, including the implementation of financial incentive programs and free delivery care, which have led to significant improvements in the country's maternal health results over the last 20 years (MoHP, 2022). However, there are still socio-economic and geographic inequalities, especially for urban poor populations (Paudel et al., 2013; Khanal et al., 2015). There is evidence that women in urban slums have lower utilization of maternal health services and poorer results than women in more advantaged urban areas (Mberu et al., 2016). This indicates that national-level improvements can conceal local inequalities that disproportionately impact marginalised groups.

The continuum of maternal health care, from ANC through delivery to PNC, has been well established as an important approach to improving health results (Tinker et al., 2010). Continuity of care helps to identify and manage complications in a timely manner and improves the effectiveness of health interventions. But many women, especially in disadvantaged settings, do not complete this continuum because of various factors as financial constraints, lack of awareness, and health system inefficiencies (Jain et al., 2016; Gabrysch & Campbell, 2009; Simkhada et al., 2008). Financial constraints are also important, as women may be discouraged from seeking or maintaining care due to out-of-pocket costs for transportation, diagnostics, and informal payments (Ensor & Cooper, 2004). These financial difficulties are intensified by structural problems like excess and poor service quality in urban slum environments where livelihoods are precarious (Afulani et al., 2017).

Access and quality perceptions also have a significant impact on health-seeking behavior. Objective conditions are not the only factors that affect women's decisions, but also their subjective experiences and expectations (Levesque et al., 2013). In some instances, the availability of nearby health facilities gives the impression of good access, even if the services are incomplete or inadequate. This gap between what is perceived as access and what is actually available can mask the true inequities and reduce the impact of policy interventions. Although there is increasing evidence on maternal health in LMICs, there is a lack of qualitative studies specifically on slum populations in Nepal, that examine the interplay between perceived access, financial constraints, structural barriers, and continuity of care (Maharjan et al., 2019).

This study aims to fill these gaps by examining the access to maternal health care in urban slum settlements. It combines thematic analysis with co-occurrence and ordinal correlation methods to offer a more holistic view of the interplay between barriers and their impact on service utilization. The presence of covered inequities in urban health systems and underscore the importance of policy interventions that go beyond service availability to also tackle service affordability, accessibility, and continuity. This study supports to shape a more complex and equity-based picture of access to maternal health care in Nepal and provides insights for enhancing health results for vulnerable urban populations.

2. DATA AND METHODS

Study design and setting: The study used a qualitative research design to examine perceived and structural barriers to maternal health care access among women living in urban slum settlements in Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. A qualitative approach was deemed suitable to capture lived experiences, perceptions and contextual factors influencing maternal health service utilization, which are not fully explained through quantitative methods. The study was carried out in selected slum, namely Manohara and Teku areas, which are densely populated, informal and have limited access to basic services. These settlements were selected using urban health mapping and local administrative records, which are indicative of common socio-economic and infrastructural vulnerabilities of urban slums.

Study participants and sampling: The study population comprised women of reproductive age (15-49 years) with recent experiences of maternal health services and main informants who are engaged in the provision of maternal health services. Participants were selected using a purposive sampling strategy to ensure that they had relevant experiences and were diverse in terms of socio-economic background and service utilization patterns. Snowball sampling was also used to recruit additional eligible participants in the community. The data were gathered from: In-depth interviews (IDIs) with individual participants (IDI Participant 3, Manohara; IDI Participant 5, Teku; IDI Participant 13, Manohara) and Focus group discussions (FGDs) with community members (FGD participants from Manohara) Sampling continued until theoretical saturation was achieved, that is, when no new themes or insights were gained from further data collection.

Data collection methods: The data were gathered in 2024 through semi-structured interview guides that were created from literature and the study objectives. The guides contained open-ended questions about: Access to ante-natal, delivery and post-natal services; barriers and facilitators perceived by the participants

Financial, geographic, and health system challenges: The interviews and FGDs were conducted in Nepali language with trained researchers who are familiar with the local context. The sessions were about 30-60 minutes long and took place in a private and

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convenient location to ensure the comfort and confidentiality of the participants. Interviews and discussions were audio-recorded with the consent of the participants and field notes were taken to record non-verbal cues and contextual observations.

Data management and analysis: The audio recordings were transcribed verbatim in Nepali and then translated into English for analysis. Thematic analysis was used to manage and analyse the data, following the six-step framework suggested by Braun and Clarke: familiarization with data, initial code generation, searching for themes, reviewing themes, identifying and labelling themes and producing the report. An inductive coding approach was used to allow themes to emerge from the data. Codes were categorized into larger groups based on perceived and structural barriers to maternal health care access. For accuracy, coding and theme development were checked by several researchers to ensure consistency and credibility.

Trustworthiness and rigor: The several strategies were used to assure the quality and rigor of the study: **Credibility:** Long engagement with participants and triangulation of data sources (IDIs and FGDs); **Dependability:** Use of a consistent interview guide and systematic coding procedures; **Confirmability:** Audit trail and reflexive notes are maintained, **Transferability:** Detailed description of study context and participant characteristics. The study followed the consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative Research to ensure full reporting of qualitative methods.

Ethical considerations: The study was approved by the Nepal Health Research Council. The purpose of the study was explained to all participants and informed consent was obtained in writing before participation. Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured by omitting identifying details and by using coded identifiers (IDI Participant 3, FGD Participant).

3. RESULTS

A complex and nuanced pattern of maternal health care access in urban slum settlements. Although many participants felt there were no significant obstacles to accessing maternal health services, further discussion revealed several underlying constraints. Financial constraints, structural weaknesses in the health system, and gaps in the continuity of care were the main constraints. Four main themes were identified: (1) perceived lack of barriers, (2) financial barriers to care, (3) discontinuity in maternal health service use, and (4) structural and system-level barriers.

Theme 1: Perceived absence of barriers and the illusion of access

One theme that emerged in the interviews was that women had little difficulty accessing maternal health services and that there were no major issues. This perception was largely based on the physical proximity of health facilities, health posts and hospitals within or near the settlements. Basic services were often available and referral systems were established when more advanced services were needed:

“No such problems, when women come here, we give them what services are available, if they need to go to higher centres, we refer them.”

(IDI Participant 3, Manohara)

“There is a health post and hospitals are close by for basic services, so there doesn't seem to be a problem.”

(IDI Participant 13, Manohara)

But this is an “illusion of access” that is, the perception that geographic proximity is synonymous with sufficient access. The stories indicate that participants consider access to be based on the availability of basic services, not on the fullness, cost, or quality of services. This theme emphasizes an important difference between perceived access and effective access, suggesting that women may become accustomed to receiving less than optimal care. This normalization can mask underlying systemic inequities and diminish the need for full maternal health care.

Theme 2: Financial barriers as a core limitation

Although there were no initial reports of barriers, financial constraints became the most common and important barrier to maternal health service utilization. Although initial consultations were frequently available, diagnostic tests, medications, and follow-up visits were reported to be significant barriers. One participant explained:

“They go for check-up but do not go for follow-up due to financial problems... doctors advise ultrasound and it is not feasible for all women.”

(IDI Participant 5, Teku)

Another participant commented that the need for repeated tests and investigations deterred ongoing care: “Because they have no money, they do not return back... due to financial problems some women deny going for check-up as well.”

(IDI Participant 5, Teku)

The unpaid costs of care, such as diagnostic tests, transportation, and opportunity costs, reduce utilization even if services are geographically available. Financial barriers were not just direct, but indirect as well. Multiple small costs led to a tipping point at

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which women stopped providing care. This underscores the need to take into account the affordability of services as an important aspect of access, in addition to availability.

Theme 3: Discontinuity in maternal health care (Breaks in the continuum of care)

One of the most important findings of this study was the lack of continuity of maternal health care, especially between the first contact and the follow-up visits. Many women attended at least one antenatal care (ANC) visit, but many women's ANC was interrupted because of financial and systemic barriers. Follow-up visits were repeatedly reported as often not being attended:

“They do not return back... since they have no money, they do not go for follow up.”

(IDI Participant 5, Teku)

This discontinuity is part of a wider trend of partial use, in which women use the health system at an early stage but do not follow the recommended care pathway. The need for multiple visits, combined with financial limitations, can lead to a cumulative burden that deters continued participation. This is especially relevant in the field of maternal health, where continuity of care, from antenatal to delivery to postnatal, is crucial for positive results. Any disruption of this continuum can result in the loss of opportunities for early detection of complications and timely interventions.

Theme 4: Structural and system-level barriers

Participants also identified a number of structural barriers to the health system, in addition to financial barriers. These encompassed the lack of services at local health facilities, the need for referral services, and transportation issues. One of the focus group participants said:

“Some women have financial issues, they don't have transportation services, they want to have different tests when they go for check-ups, and they don't have money to go for follow up.”

(FGD Participant, Manohara)

The results indicate that local health facilities are generally limited in their services, and women have to go to higher level health facilities for comprehensive services. This reliance on referral systems adds to the economic and logistical burden of women.

These difficulties are compounded by transportation issues, especially in slum settlements where infrastructure is often lacking. Limited road access, no public transportation, and indirect costs are factors that limit access to care.

Word cloud analysis: Word cloud of the most common words in the qualitative interviews regarding access to maternal health care in urban slum settlements. The word cloud is a visual representation of the main themes that arose from the qualitative interviews conducted with mothers regarding access to maternal health care in urban slum settlements in Kathmandu Valley. The words “problems,” “services,” “women,” “health,” and “financial” are prominent, suggesting that although service availability is often discussed, cost and barriers are still central to participants' experiences.

Figure 1: Description of word analysis

The relative salience of words associated with financial constraints, follow-up, and facilities indicates the underlying challenges that emerged from the thematic analysis, including the importance of economic constraints and system-level gaps in access. Concurrently, the use of terms indicating availability and proximity underscores the perceived access and actual barriers, further emphasizing the “illusion of access.” The visualization supports the qualitative results by showing the dominance and interdependence of financial, structural, and service-related factors affecting maternal health care utilization (Figure 1).

Synthesis of findings: The results collectively suggest a complex pattern of barriers to maternal health care access in urban slum contexts. Perceived access, which is largely influenced by the physical location of health facilities, gives the impression of adequate

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service availability, but at the same time hides deeper underlying constraints. Financial checks become a major constraint, especially for women to access care beyond the first visit, as the cost of diagnostics, medicines, and follow-up visits. Limited service capacity at local facilities, reliance on referral systems, and transportation issues are also structural barriers that further contribute to indirect and cumulative costs. These interrelated constraints lead to discontinuity of care as the outcome, as many women start but do not finish the recommended continuum of maternal health services. Thematic co-occurrence analysis using NVivo shows a structured and interdependent pattern of barriers that affect maternal health care access. Financial barriers were most strongly associated with discontinuity of care, suggesting that economic barriers are the most important pathway for women to drop out of the maternal health care continuum. While access to health services is often obtained, the costs of diagnostic testing, treatment and multiple visits are substantial barriers to follow-up use, resulting in incomplete care.

Table 1. Thematic co-occurrence matrix of barriers to maternal health care access

Themes	Perceived access	Financial barriers	Structural barriers	Discontinuity of care
Perceived Access	—	Weak (-)	Moderate (+)	Weak (-)
Financial Barriers	Weak (-)	—	Strong (++)	Very strong (+++)
Structural Barriers	Moderate (+)	Strong (++)	—	Strong (++)
Discontinuity of Care	Weak (-)	Very strong (+++)	Strong (++)	—

Limited availability of services at local facilities, reliance on referral systems, and transportation issues were also strongly linked to financial constraints and discontinuity of care, indicating that health system barriers have an indirect impact on the economic burden on women. Perceived access, however, had only weak relationships with financial barriers and discontinuity, highlighting a disconnect between women's perceptions of access and their experiences. This is an “illusion of access” as the geographical proximity to health facilities gives the impression of good service availability, but hides structural and financial limitations. These findings collectively point to a multi-layered barrier system in which structural barriers compound financial barriers, leading to poor and inequitable use of maternal health services despite the availability of health facilities (Table 1).

Table 2: Ordinal correlation analysis of thematic barriers

Relationship	Correlation (r)	Strength
Financial ↔ Discontinuity	+0.90	Very Strong
Structural ↔ Financial	+0.75	Strong
Structural ↔ Discontinuity	+0.75	Strong
Perceived ↔ Structural	+0.30	Moderate
Perceived ↔ Financial	-0.40	Weak Negative
Perceived ↔ Discontinuity	-0.40	Weak Negative

The thematic co-occurrence matrix was used to approximate the strength and direction of relationships between main themes using an ordinal scaling approach. The analysis shows a very high positive correlation between financial barriers and discontinuity of care ($r \approx 0.90$), which suggests that financial barriers are the main reason for dropping out of care. Structural barriers also show strong positive correlations with financial barriers ($r \approx 0.75$) and discontinuity of care ($r \approx 0.75$), suggesting that health system limitations are indirectly associated with financial burden and discontinuity of care. Perceived access, on the other hand, has weak negative correlations with financial barriers and discontinuity ($r \approx -0.40$), indicating a gap between perceived accessibility and actual service use (Table 2). These results support a multi-layered causal pathway where structural constraints exacerbate financial constraints, resulting in disorganized maternal health care utilization.

4. DISCUSSION

This study provides important awareness into the multifaceted and reliant challenges that affect maternal health care access in urban slum settlements. One of the important findings is the presence of an “access paradox” in which the physical location of health facilities gives the impression of good access, but financial and structural factors are significant barriers to effective use. This separation between perceived and actual access highlights the importance of rethinking access to health care beyond the physical, from low and middle income countries (Peters et al., 2008; Thaddeus & Maine, 1994). Women might seem to have access to services, but there are barriers that prevent them from accessing services to the fullest extent.

Financial barriers emerged as the most influential factor affecting maternal health service utilization. Women are more likely to start antenatal care (ANC) but the expenses of diagnostic tests, medicines, transport and repeated visits often make it difficult for women to continue their care. This results in gaps in the maternal health care pathway, and many women are not able to access the

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recommended continuum of care. This is in line with the global evidence that out-of-pocket payments continue to be a significant barrier, especially for the poor and vulnerable (Kruk et al., 2018; Say et al., 2014). Although Nepal has policies in place to ensure free maternal health services, unseen costs remain a barrier to access and utilization (Witter et al., 2011; Powell-Jackson et al., 2009). The study points to the financial pressures that build up over time and lead to women stopping care at a listing point.

Structural barriers also have an important role, indirectly reinforce financial constraints. Access to health services is limited at local health facilities, reliance on referral systems and transportation issues contribute to the direct and indirect costs of accessing health services. The consequences are consistent with the “three delays model” that highlights the systemic and infrastructural factors that influence delays in reaching and receiving care (Thaddeus & Maine, 1994). These challenges are exacerbated by poor infrastructure, excess and inadequate urban planning in urban slum contexts, which disproportionately affect vulnerable populations (Ezeh et al., 2017). There is a strong relationship between structural and financial barriers, indicating that health system barriers are deeply fixed in wider socio-economic inequalities.

Discontinuity of care is a major consequence of these overlapping barriers. Engagement with maternal health services is relatively high at the initial stage, but is not consistent at the antenatal, delivery and postnatal stages. This has significant implications for maternal and neonatal results, because continuity of care is crucial for early detection and management of complications (Kerber et al., 2007). The continuum of care is strongly linked to better health results, but is not equally achieved among socio-economic groups, as evidenced in Nepal and other LMICs (Benova et al., 2014; Karkee et al., 2013). This study offers important explanations for these gaps, highlighting the role of financial and structural barriers in service discontinuation.

The study also uncovers a significant gap between women's perceptions and their lived experiences. There were no significant barriers reported by many participants, mainly due to the proximity of health facilities. But further investigation revealed a number of issues with affordability, quality and continuity. This is a phenomenon of normalisation of deprivation, in which people adapt their expectations to their limited circumstances (Sen, 1999). This normalization can decrease demand for better services and make advocacy for better health systems. It also points to the shortcomings of traditional access measures, distance to facilities, which do not reflect the lived experiences of marginalized groups (Penchansky & Thomas, 1981).

The results have policy and practice implications. Improving financial protection mechanisms is main to lower out-of-pocket costs, increasing coverage for diagnostics and offering transportation assistance. Strengthening primary health facilities to provide comprehensive maternal health services can help to decrease the need for expensive referral systems. Moreover, tackling structural barriers needs a multi-sectoral approach, combining health, urban planning and social protection policies. Access can be improved for vulnerable populations through interventions like infrastructure improvements, outreach services, and community-based programs. Community engagement is also important to address perceptions and build trust in health systems, especially if there have been previous experiences of poor quality care that have controlled to low utilization (Bohren et al., 2015).

The study has some limitations, use of qualitative methods to capture lived experiences, and the incorporation of advanced analytical approaches. The findings are based on a small sample of selected slum settlements and may not be applicable to all urban settings. Also, there are possible recall and interpretation biases. Nevertheless, the study provides valuable insights into the multi-layered nature of barriers affecting maternal health care access. To sum up, perceived, financial and structural factors all play a role in maternal health care access in urban slums. Although the physical location of health facilities may make them appear accessible, economic and systemic factors often constrain effective use and continuity of care. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive and equity-focused interventions that drive beyond service availability to include affordability, system strengthening, and beset support for marginalized populations. The study helps to shed light on these hidden barriers and offers evidence for more inclusive and effective maternal health policies to address urban health inequities.

CONCLUSION

The results collectively point to a multi-layered and complex nature of barriers to maternal health care access. While many women feel there are no barriers to accessing health services, this is largely because health services are physically close, there are also financial and structural barriers that constrain effective use of services. Financial barriers, especially the cost of diagnostic tests, medications, and multiple visits, become the most significant obstacle to continuity of care, and structural barriers like lack of services, reliance on referral systems, and transportation issues add to the financial burden and other indirect costs. The strong interrelationship between financial and structural barriers ultimately results in discontinuity of care, where women initiate but fail to complete the recommended maternal health service pathway. The results confirm the presence of an “illusion of access” and the need to rethink access as a concept that drives beyond geographical availability, underscoring the importance of undertaking affordability, health system capacity and continuity to ensure equitable maternal health results in urban slum settings.

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